

EXPLORING THE CONNECTION BETWEEN MARITAL SATISFACTION, SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE, AGGRESSION, AND LOCUS OF CONTROL

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10159412](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159412)

Abstract

The present study focused on examining the potential links between marital contentment and several factors, including social media usage, aggressive behaviour, and locus of control. The research sample comprised 200 participants from the Darbhanga district in Bihar, who were selected through a purposive-cum-incident sampling technique. The Kansas Marital Satisfaction Scale (KMS), Scale of Social Networking Usage, Bhardwaj's Aggression Scale, and Rotter's Locus of Control Scale were employed to assess the variables of interest. The collected data was analysed using the Pearson correlation method. The findings indicated that social media usage, aggressive behaviour, and locus of control had a negative association with marital satisfaction. The study's results provide crucial insights into the factors that can impact marital relationships, particularly in the context of contemporary social media usage.

Keywords: Marital Satisfaction, Social Media Usage, Aggression and Locus of Control.

INTRODUCTION

Marriage can bring immense happiness or distress to individuals, making its significance undeniable. The success of a marriage depends on the compatibility of the couple and the level of satisfaction they experience from it. Typically, marriage is a legal and socially approved union between a man and a woman. However, same-sex marriages are also becoming more accepted in society and the law. The study of the relationship between marriage and various variables is important, given its importance in our lives. Marriage is happy and stable when both partners are satisfied with each other. Marital satisfaction plays a crucial role in determining the overall success of a marriage. When a marriage is marked by high marital satisfaction, the couples are content with their union and likely to stay together for a long time. According to Baumeister & Vohs (2007), marital satisfaction is a mental state that reflects how a person perceives the benefits and costs of marriage. If a marriage partner causes more costs than benefits, the person is less likely to be satisfied with the marriage and the partner. Conversely, if the perceived benefits are more significant, the person will likely be more satisfied with the marriage and the partner. The interaction between couples can be positive or negative, influenced by personality traits, emotional intelligence, forgiveness, and sacrifice. Therefore, how one interacts with one's spouse mainly depends on many factors.

The research found that 42% of unmarried individuals in romantic relationships and 25% of those who were married or in partnerships reported that their partners spent more time on their mobile phones during their time together (Lenhart & Duggan, 2014). A 2015 survey revealed that 90% of respondents in the United States had used their

phones during their most recent social activity, while 86% had observed others doing the same (Lenhart et al., 2015). The term "phubbing" describes individuals checking their phones during conversations, leading to a breakdown in interpersonal communication (Davey et al., 2018; Aljasir, 2022). The combination of the words "snubbing" and "phone" is used to describe excessive smartphone use (Pendergrass & Town, 2017), while being "phubbed" refers to feeling neglected by someone who is engrossed in their phone (Chotpitayasunondh & Douglas, 2018). The internet and social media use harm marital satisfaction (Tong et al., 2021), with physical aggression and marital satisfaction closely linked (Lawrence & Bradbury, 2007; Testa & Leonard, 2001; Rogge & Bradbury, 1999). Aggression is defined as physical or verbal behaviour aimed at harming someone (Baron & Richardson, 1994), and intentional harm is more hurtful than unintentional, even if the degree of harm is the same (Ames & Fiske, 2013). Adolescents and children may exhibit aggressive behaviours, such as throwing tantrums or intentionally hurting others. The locus of control, or the belief that one's actions influence the outcome of events, is associated with marital satisfaction, with a higher level of internal locus of control in wives leading to greater marital satisfaction (Bugaighis et al., 1983; Lee & McKinnish, 2019; Myers & Booth, 1999). Few studies have explored the relationship between marital satisfaction, social media use, aggression, and locus of control, particularly in the Indian culture.

METHODOLOGY

The study has been conducted with the following objectives:

- 1) To measure the connection between social media usage and marital satisfaction.
- 2) To evaluate the association between aggressive behaviour and marital satisfaction.
- 3) To assess the relationship between locus of control and marital satisfaction.

Based on the above objectives and reviewed studies, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

- 1) There will be a negative correlation between social media usage and marital satisfaction.
- 2) Aggressive behaviour and marital satisfaction will be negatively associated with each other.
- 3) Locus of control and marital satisfaction will have a significant association.

Sample

We conducted a study in the Darbhanga district, surveying 200 married individuals using purposive-cum-incident sampling. The participants ranged in age from 25 to 62 years old, representing various age groups. The average age of the participants was 44 years, with a standard deviation of 12 years. Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics of the participants' ages. The pie chart illustrates the age distribution of the sample, and the histogram indicates that the sample follows a normal distribution.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the age of the participants

N	300
Mean	44
Median	45
Std. Deviation	12
Skewness	0.0625
Std. Error of Skewness	.145
Kurtosis	1.1569
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.413
Range	40
Minimum	25
Maximum	65

Graph 1: PIECHART OF AGE

Graph 2: Histogram of the age with normal probability

Instruments

The following instruments/scales have been used:

- 1) Kansas Marital Satisfaction Scale (KMS) – This scale has only three items that are responded to on a 7-point scale on the basis of degree of agreement or disagreement. The range of the score is 3 to 21.
- 2) Scale of social networking usage - It has 24 items. It measures four aspects of social networking site usage: academic, socialization, entertainment, informativeness, and constraints.
- 3) Bhardwaj’s Aggression Scale – This scale has been developed by R. L. Bhardwaj and published by the National Psychological Corporation, Agra. It has 28 items.
- 4) Rotter’s Locus of Control Scale – This scale has 29 forced-choice items. Scores of the items range from 0 to 13, where a lower score means the internal locus of control, and a higher score indicates the external locus of control. Internal consistency estimates were relatively stable
- 5) Personal Information Form - The researcher prepared the personal information form and received the respondents’ socio-demographics.

Procedure for data collection

The participants were contacted, questionnaires were distributed, and responses were recorded one by one.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Marital satisfaction and social media usage

Hypothesis number 1 predicted a link between marital satisfaction and social media usage, stating that the two would have a negative correlation. To test this, a Pearson correlation was performed on marital satisfaction and social media usage variables. The resulting data is recorded in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation between Marital satisfaction and Social media usage

Correlations		Social Media Usage
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	-0.194*
	N	200
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).		
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).		

In Table 2, it is demonstrated that there is a correlation between social media usage and marital satisfaction. The coefficient of correlation is -0.194, indicating a negative relationship between the two variables. This relationship is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. It means that when participants increase their social media usage, their marital satisfaction decreases. Conversely, their marital satisfaction tends to improve if they spend less time on social media. Therefore, we can accept the first hypothesis that there is a negative correlation between social media usage and marital satisfaction, which is consistent with the findings of Chotpitayasunondh & Douglas (2018) and Tong et al. (2021).

Marital satisfaction and aggressive behaviour

The second hypothesis posited a connection between marital satisfaction and aggressive behaviour, suggesting a negative correlation between the two variables. A Pearson correlation was performed to assess this claim, and the resulting data is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation between Marital satisfaction and Aggressive behaviour

Correlations		Aggression
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	-0.1894*
	N	200
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).		
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).		

Table 3 displays the correlation between Marital satisfaction and aggression, revealing a statistically significant negative correlation coefficient of -0.1894 at a 0.05 level. This indicates that as participants' aggression increases, their marital satisfaction decreases. Conversely, when they exhibit less aggressive behaviour, their marital satisfaction improves. Thus, the acceptance of the second hypothesis, which states that "aggressive behaviour and marital satisfaction will be negatively associated with each other," is consistent with previous research conducted by Lawrence & Bradbury, 2007 and Testa & Leonard, 2001.

Marital satisfaction and locus of control

The association between marital satisfaction and locus of control has been predicted in hypothesis number 3. It said there would be a significant relationship between locus of control and marital satisfaction. For testing this statement, Pearson correlation was calculated between the two variables, i.e. marital satisfaction and locus of control. The obtained result is recorded in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation between Marital satisfaction and Locus of control

Correlations		Locus of control
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	-0.186*
	N	200
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).		
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).		

The fourth table provides information on the correlation between marital satisfaction and locus of control. The coefficient of correlation between the two variables is negative at -0.186, and this relationship is statistically significant at a 0.05 level. The correlation direction indicates that as participants' locus of control increases, their marital satisfaction decreases, and vice versa. Locus of control has two dimensions: internal and external. A low score on the Rotter's Locus of Control Scale indicates an internal locus of control, while a high score indicates an external locus of control. If people perceive an internal locus of control, their marital satisfaction increases but decreases if they perceive an external locus of control. Therefore, the third hypothesis, which states that locus of control and marital satisfaction have a significant association, is accepted. This might be because individuals with an internal locus of control try to improve their married life's quality since they believe they can change the outcome of their life events. On the other hand, individuals with an external locus of control may be hesitant to improve their marital life since they believe they cannot

change anything in their life. Similar results were reported in the investigation by Bugaighis et al. (1983) and Lee & McKinnish (2019).

CONCLUSION

It is imperative to acknowledge that the conclusions derived from this study are founded upon restricted sample size, and a non-random sampling methodology was employed. Furthermore, the sample only consisted of individuals from a single city in Bihar. The conclusions drawn from the study are as follows:

- 1) Marital satisfaction and social media usage are negatively associated. They must limit social media usage to enhance the satisfaction of married life.
- 2) Aggressive behaviour decreases marital satisfaction or vice-versa because a negative correlation exists between both.
- 3) Marital satisfaction increases in the presence of an internal locus of control but decreases in the case of an external locus of control.

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